

Preparation of Optically Active Unsymmetrical Ketones from (+) Acid Halide

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Optically active unsymmetrical aliphatic ketones of the type $R \cdot CO \cdot \overset{*}{\underset{\text{CH}_3}{\text{C}}} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3$, where R represents different alkyl groups, have been prepared by the Grignard reaction, using anhydrous CdCl_2 and (+)-1-methyl butyryl chloride. Similarly optically active unsymmetrical ketones of the type $\text{Ar} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \overset{*}{\underset{\text{CH}_3}{\text{C}}} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3$, where Ar represents phenyl and substituted phenyl groups, have also been prepared by the Friedel Craft's reaction using (+)-1-methyl butyryl chloride and different aromatic hydrocarbon. The specific and molecular rotations of these ketones have been determined.

For this purpose optically active (+)-1-methyl butyric acid $[\alpha]_D^{35} + 12 \cdot 15^\circ$ ($l = 1$) was prepared by the oxidation of (+)-2-methyl butan-1-ol $[\alpha]_D^{35} - 4 \cdot 69^\circ$ ($l = 1$), obtained by fractional distillation of fusel oil through a column. The acid was converted to the (+)-acid halide by PCl_3 . By the interaction of (+)-1-methyl butyryl chloride, with the Grignard complex prepared from different alkyl halides in the presence of anhydrous CdCl_2 , optically active unsymmetrical ketones have been obtained. Further (+)-1-methyl butyryl chloride yields optically active unsymmetrical aromatic ketones by the Friedel-Craft's reaction, using anhydrous AlCl_3 and benzene and substituted benzene derivatives. The specific and molecular rotations of these unsymmetrical ketones have been recorded in Table 1 and Table 2.

In the alkyl ketones the minimum rotation, $[\text{M}]_D^{35} + 211 \cdot 20^\circ$, was observed in the case of 2,4-dimethyl-hexan-3-one, while maximum rotation, $[\text{M}]_D^{35} + 739 \cdot 80^\circ$, was observed in the case of 3-methyl-heptan-4-one. In the aryl ketones the minimum rotation, $[\text{M}]_D^{35} + 178 \cdot 60^\circ$, was observed in the case of 1-methyl-propyl *p*-ethyl phenyl ketone, while maximum rotation, $[\text{M}]_D^{35} + 147 \cdot 3^\circ$ was observed in the case of 1-methyl propyl *p*-ethoxy phenyl ketone.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

(+)-1-Methyl butyric acid: To a mixture of 2-methyl butan-1-ol (88 gm; 1 mole; $[\alpha]_D^{35} - 4 \cdot 69^\circ$ ($l = 1$)) and sodium carbonate (17 gm. in 100 ml. water) potassium permanganate (125 gm. in 1500 ml. water) was added during 4 hrs. and the mixture was further stirred for 4 hrs., kept overnight and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated on a waterbath and acidified with 50% sulphuric acid and the organic acid extracted with chloroform (50 ml. \times 2). The chloroform layer was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, chloroform removed and the acid was distilled at $135^\circ/15$ mm. yield 57%; d_4^{35} 0.9179; n_D^{35} 1.442, $[\alpha]_D^{35} + 12 \cdot 15^\circ$ ($l = 1$).

(+)-1-Methyl butyryl chloride: The (+)-1-methyl butyric acid (51 gm., 0.5 mole) and PCl_3 (42 gm, 0.25 mole) were refluxed together at $80-90^\circ$ for 2 hr. The upper colourless layer was decanted from the syrupy residue and distilled at $115-120^\circ$, yield 89%; d_4^{35} 0.8219, n_D^{35} 1.427. $[\alpha]_D^{35} + 12 \cdot 38^\circ$ ($l = 1$).

General methods for the preparation of optically active ketones: Alkyl ketones: To an icecold solution of the Grignard reagent, prepared from alkyl halide (0.2 mole) and magnesium (0.2 mole) in ether (100 ml) was added anhydrous CdCl_2 (19.6 gm., 1.08 mole) during 5 min. and the contents refluxed for 20 min. The ether was distilled and to the residual mass dry benzene (65 ml) was added, the mixture was refluxed until a homogeneous solution resulted. To this was added (+)-1-methyl butyryl chloride (19 gm., 0.16 mole) rapidly at 10–15°. The reaction mass stirred vigorously for 20 min and then decomposed with ice and sulphuric acid (15%). The product was extracted with benzene, washed with sodium carbonate solution (5%), water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After removal of benzene the residue was distilled at 15–20 mm pressure to yield the ketones.

Aryl ketones: The reaction was carried out as usual by the interaction of (+)-1-methyl butyryl chloride (41 gm, 0.34 mole) and aromatic hydrocarbon (1.03 mole) using anhydrous AlCl_3 (40 gm.). The ketones and their optical rotations are in Table 2.

TABLE 1

R	Yield %	B.P. 15–20 mm.	Molecular		Density	Ref. index	Formula	Optically active unsymmetrical ketones of the type $\text{R}-\text{CO}-\overset{\text{CH}_3}{\underset{*}{\text{C}}}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$			
			$[\alpha]_D^{25}$ (l = 1) in degree	rotation $[\text{M}]_D^{25}$				Required		Found	
								C%	H%	C%	H%
Methyl	71	130	+4.47	+447.00	0.8193	1.423	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$	72.00	12.00	71.76	11.61
Ethyl	69	140	+4.09	+466.30	0.8110	1.421	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$	73.69	12.28	72.90	12.77
n-Propyl	67	151	+5.08	+650.30	0.8210	1.428	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$	75.00	12.53	74.71	12.13
i-Propyl	44	150	+1.65	+211.20	0.8097	1.420	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$	75.00	12.53	75.30	12.14
n-Butyl	73	165	+5.21	+739.80	0.8290	1.431	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$	76.05	12.68	76.35	12.79
i-Butyl	40	160	+3.94	+559.50	0.8206	1.424	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$	76.05	12.68	76.49	11.96
n-Amyl	68	185	+2.62	+408.70	0.8426	1.437	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$	76.93	12.82	76.72	12.09
i-Amyl	35	180	+3.32	+517.80	0.8226	1.429	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$	76.93	12.82	76.52	12.34
n-Octyl	65	205	+1.88	+353.50	0.8426	1.439	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$	78.77	13.13	79.06	13.72

TABLE 2

Ar.	Yield %	B.P. 15–20 mm.	Molecular		Density	Ref. index	Formula	Optically active unsymmetrical ketones of the type $\text{Ar}.\text{CO}.\overset{\text{CH}_3}{\underset{*}{\text{C}}}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$			
			$[\alpha]_D^{25}$ (l = 1) in degrees	$[\text{M}]_D^{25}$ (l = 1) in degrees				Required		Found	
								C%	H%	C%	H%
C_6H_5	65	135	+5.10	+826.20	1.098	1.447	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$	81.49	8.642	81.02	8.25
p- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	55	165	+4.43	+779.6	1.101	1.478	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$	81.83	9.09	81.28	8.83
p- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	50	180	+0.94	+178.6	1.159	1.495	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$	82.10	9.473	81.65	9.21
p-Cl. C_6H_4	58	175	+3.99	+784.1	1.147	1.488	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{OCl}$	67.17	6.615	67.73	6.45
p-Br. C_6H_4	60	130	+3.730	+898.9	1.159	1.498	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{OBr}$	54.78	5.394	54.32	5.23
p-1:3(CH_3) ₂ C_6H_3	62	190	—	—	1.236	1.482	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$	82.10	9.473	81.86	9.23
o-1:4 CH_3 (CH_3) ₂ C_6H_3	50	198	+1.35	+294.3	1.159	1.496	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$	82.56	10.09	82.08	9.87
p- $\text{CH}_3\text{O}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	55	160	+3.20	+614.4	1.179	1.518	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$	75.01	8.333	74.63	8.19
p- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	58	175	+7.15	+1473.0	1.159	1.498	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$	75.71	8.738	75.23	8.65